

ISic3082

I.Sicily inscription 3082

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

limestone (breccia)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0973b

Manganaro, G. 1988. Le tavole finanziarie di Tauromenion. In Knoepfler, D. (eds.), *Comptes et inventaires dans la cité grecque: actes du colloque international d'épigraphique tenu à Neuchâtel du 23 au 26 septembre 1986 en l'honneur de J.Tréheux*. Neuchâtel. pp. 155-190. At 156-157

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